

ПОРІВННЯ СХЕМ НЕАД'ЮВАНТОЇ ХІМІОТЕРАПІЇ FLOT ТА CAPOX ПРИ РАКУ ШЛУНКУ

COMPARISON OF NEOADJUVANT CHEMOTHERAPY SCHEMES FLOT AND CAPOX IN GASTRIC CANCER

Конишева А. Ю.

Konysheva Anna

ORCID: 0000-0002-1568-8042

Національний університет охорони здоров'я України імені П. Л. Шупика

Кафедра онкології

м. Київ, Україна

Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine

Department of oncology

Kyiv, Ukraine

e-mail: konysheva.anna@ukr.net

Today, gastric cancer (GC) is one of the most pressing problems of modern oncology, as the incidence and mortality of patients from this pathology remain high. According to the National Cancer Registry, in Ukraine in 2019 the incidence of cervical cancer was 19 cases per 100 thousand population (25 - men and 14 - women); the mortality rate was 14 (20 and 10.6, respectively), which is significantly higher than the European level (14 and 10, respectively). 31% of patients with cancer were diagnosed in stages I-II, in 22% of patients - were in stage III. During the period 2019-20, 21 cases per 100,000 population were registered, and 53% of patients with the first diagnosis died within the first year, so this pathology remains one of the most important medical and socio-economic problems.

Despite previous studies in the optimization of chemotherapy, at present, this question remains relevant, as the frequency of objective response to systemic chemotherapy does not exceed 14-25% with a median survival of 8-12 months.

There are currently three main clinical trials of combination therapy with preoperative chemotherapy: MAGIC [1], FNCLCC / FFCD 9703 [2], and FLOT4 [3].

To date, there is no single solution for the optimal choice of neoadjuvant chemotherapy to be combined with surgery in patients with resectable breast cancer, in order to reduce the size of the tumor, thus achieving the possibility of less traumatic surgery.

Regarding the conducted research, few have highlighted the very possibility of conducting neoadjuvant chemotherapy within 4 courses with subsequent surgical treatment in the CAPOX and FLOT schemes, so this issue remains under consideration.

The purpose of this study is to compare the results of both histopathological and general for the possibility of choosing a more optimal scheme.

We collected and analyzed data from 32 patients. These are patients with resectable gastric cancer who received neoadjuvant chemotherapy with subsequent surgical treatment.

Inclusion criteria were gastric cancer stage I-III, age 20-80 years, and ECOG 0-I, I-II.

In the first group, patients received neoadjuvant chemotherapy according to the FLOT scheme (docetaxel 50 mg / m² iv, drip, on the 1st day + oxaliplatin 85 mg / m² on the 1st day + leucovorin 200 mg / m², 2 hours, iv infusion, on the 1st day + 5-FU 400 mg / m² iv, jet, on the 1st day + 5-FU 2400 mg / m², iv infusion, 46–48 hours, on the 1st day Repeat the cycle every two weeks), in the second-CAPOX (capecitabine 1000 mg / m² 2 times a day orally from the 1st to the 14th day of the cycle or from the evening of the first day to the morning of the 15th day of the cycle + oxaliplatin 100- 130 mg / m² iv, drip, on day 1. Repeat every 3 weeks).

During the study, patients received all recommendations for concomitant therapy. Also, biochemical and general blood tests were performed and monitored after each cycle.

At the end of the neoadjuvant chemotherapy course, studies were performed, such as FGDS and CT with intravenous observation to determine the response of the tumor to treatment. Clinical efficacy was determined according to the criteria for assessing the response in solid tumors (RECIST v1.1) [4]. Response criteria included complete tumor regression, partial regression, disease stabilization, and disease progression.

Morphological complete regression was determined in patients who did not have all the signs of cancer in the drugs and the lymph nodes obtained. Radical resection (R0) was defined as resection with microscopically negative resection edges, without tumor signs at the macroscopic and microscopic levels. The presence of a positive resection edge at the microscopic level in the absence of such signs was macroscopically defined as R1 resection.

Prescribed chemotherapy regimens were accompanied by grade 3-4 adverse reactions in more patients (55%). Nausea, vomiting, and general weakness were found in 12%, and thrombocytopenia and neutropenia in 20%.

80% of patients had neoadjuvant chemotherapy completion, others underwent surgery at the end of the 3rd year, this is primarily due to the high toxicity of the drugs and severe side effects.

Based on our results, we can conclude that both of the proposed schemes of neoadjuvant chemotherapy are almost equally highly toxic and make it impossible to conduct timely surgery, which carries an increased risk of early metastasis and recurrence. This prompts us to further study and find the optimal scheme of neoadjuvant chemotherapy.

Literature

1 . Cunningham, D., Allum, W. H., Stenning, S.P. Thompson, J. N., Van de Velde, C. J., Nicolson, M., ..., Chua, Y. J. (2006). Perioperative chemotherapy versus

surgery alone for resectable gastroesophageal cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 355(1), 11–20. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa055531.

2. Ychou, M., Boige, V., Pignon, J.-P., Conroy, T., Bouché, O., Lebreton, G., ... Rougier, P. (2011). Perioperative chemotherapy compared with surgery alone for resectable gastroesophageal adenocarcinoma: an FNCLCC and FFCD multicenter phase III trial. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 29(13), 1715–1721. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2010.33.0597.

3. [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(18\)32557-1/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(18)32557-1/fulltext)

4. Eisenhauer, E. A., Therasse, P., Bogaerts, J., Schwartz, L. H., Sargent, D., Ford, R., ... Verweij, J. (2009). New response evaluation criteria in solid tumours: revised RECIST guideline (version 1.1). *European Journal of Cancer*, 45(2), 228–247. doi: 10.1016/j.ejca.2008.10.026.